

DRESDEN

CLIMATE-NEUTRAL BY 2030
EU MISSION CITY

The City of Dresden, in Germany, is situated in the State of Saxony, and it is characterized by Marine west coast, warm summer climate (Cfb)

With 328,28 km², Dresden has a population of 563.311 (2022), with expected moderate growth

LEADING ECONOMIC SECTORS IN DRESDEN:

KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY

TECHNOLOGY AND IT SERVICES

INDUSTRY

MAIN SOURCES OF CO₂ EMISSIONS (2022):

TRADE AND SERVICES

DOMESTIC SERVICES

TRANSPORT

MUNICIPAL ASSETS

MAIN SOURCES OF ENERGY GENERATED :

ELECTRIC ENERGY

NATURAL GAS

DISTRICT HEATING

RENEWABLES

MOBILITY PATTERNS:

AROUND 36% OF THE DISTANCES TRAVELED BY CAR, 26% BY FOOT, 20% BY PUBLIC TRANSPORT AND 18% BY BIKE

SNAPSHOT OF DRESDEN ON CAPACITY BUILDING:

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

Governance and Policy
Implementation and technology

KEY AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

Finance
Social Innovation

TOPICS OF INTEREST:

Business models for energy-related projects
Citizen and stakeholder engagement

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the European Union

NATIONAL LEVEL:
FEDERAL CLIMATE PROTECTION
LAW (2019)

IN DRESDEN:
INTER-DEPARTMENTAL
COORDINATION ON CLIMATE

CROSS SECTORAL
CLIMATE PLANS

CO-DESIGN
PROCESS WITH KEY
STAKEHOLDERS

GOVERNANCE AND POLICY

In Germany, the first Federal Climate Protection Law (CPL) was introduced in 2019. In 2021, the CLP has been updated aiming to achieve climate neutrality for 2045, anticipating the EU 2050 goal, and targeting at least –65% emission reduction by 2030. The ambitious German Climate Protection Law is also supported by multilateral coordination in the climate governance structure that facilitates the implementation of the climate target, with specific plans by sector: energy, industry, buildings, transport and agriculture.

Based on the climate goals and plans established by the Federal Government, the federal state governments and local governments share climate and environmental competencies and can set their own climate goals. A good degree of coordination among the different levels of government is ensured by specific governance mechanisms.

The City of Dresden is part of the 100 EU Mission Cities, aiming to accelerate climate-neutrality by 2030.

The governance structure on climate is led by the Environment Department and the Staff Unit for Climate Protection and Adaptation to Climate Change, facilitating the coordination among departments and supported by additional mechanisms of collaboration among units, teams, task forces, and projects.

Within the City of Dresden, climate roles and responsibilities are shared across the relevant city administration divisions dealing with the topics of: Environment & Biodiversity; Energy and Municipal Buildings; Transport, Mobility, and Infrastructure; Economic Development, Education and Sports; and all departments are directly involved in the implementation of the city climate agenda.

The municipality actively involves local entities and stakeholders in inter-sectoral consultations to co-design the action plans of the city to become climate neutral. This co-design process is structured across a Scientific Board with universities and research centers, as well as Roundtables with key actors from the private sector and civic representation.

SOCIAL INNOVATION

Dresden recognizes a key role in mobilizing its local ecosystem of stakeholders and citizens to ensure an inclusive transition. The municipality organises different types of engagement activities related to climate action from workshops to co-design sessions and assemblies with a cross-sectoral focus, such as the Public Climate Protection Forum or the current "Wärmewendedialog", which is a city-wide and multi-stage dialogue platform on the ongoing municipal heat supply planning. Among the tools is the use of digital channels, such as the Online Citizen Participation within the Integrated Energy and Climate Protection Concept.

In the pursuit of a just transition, Dresden appoints specific roles within the municipality to ensure social justice and gender equality in its participatory processes and across departments.

Despite the high priority placed on citizen and stakeholder engagement, levels of participation could be improved.

The main barriers to engagement are mostly due to a lack of structured feedback mechanisms between communities and decision-makers, a need for monitoring levels of interaction through digital communication channels, and a lack of interest in climate change.

To improve its social engagement capacity, the City of Dresden is looking to innovate in the following areas:

INNOVATIVE
COMMUNICATIONS CHANNEL
AND MONITORING TOOLS

ENGAGEMENT METHODS

PARTNERSHIPS AND COLLABORATION
WITH INTERMEDIARY LOCAL
ORGANISATIONS

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IMPLEMENTATION AND TECHNOLOGY

The City of Dresden focuses on decarbonizing its Buildings; Transport; and Energy Supply (Heat & Electric Energy).

When trying to reduce carbon emissions, Dresden faces challenges related to high upfront investment costs, slow public procurement processes, and shortages of personnel. Uncertain or unclear regulations and taxation, and the need for more targeted regulations and enabling policies are main barriers, too.

To enable emission reduction, the city focuses on digitalisation strategies, and has set targets on renewable energy production.

Cross-sectoral commitment and civic awareness are key social factors to overcome the implementation barriers.

As Lighthouse City in the project, Dresden has experience in designing and implementing Positive and Clean Energy Districts (PCEDs). The building and construction industry, the energy supply chain, and citizens are identified as essential stakeholders for a successful PCED implementation.

CLIMATE AND ENERGY DATA COLLECTION ANALYSIS

MITIGATION SECTORS

LOCAL RENEWABLE ENERGY PRODUCTION

COLLABORATION

NEUTRALPATH key target sectors for the PCEDs implementation are: Built Environment, Energy and Mobility

FINANCING AND BUSINESS MODELS FOR PCEDS AND CLIMATE NEUTRALITY

The City of Dresden has experience in energy efficiency investments and uses public funding, third-party financing, revolving funds, and innovative financing schemes on grassroots financing schemes like Crowdfunding or civic associations for civic power plants..

Based on the financing gaps identified, Dresden is seeking to enhance its financing skills in mixing different financial schemes and tools, mobilizing private investment, and developing effective business models for energy-related projects.

As part of its Climate City Contract under the EU Climate Neutral and Smart Cities Mission, Dresden will develop an Investment Plan as a comprehensive long-term economic and financial strategy to achieve climate neutrality by 2030.

KEY COMPETENCE AREAS:

- Third-party financing
- Citizen Finance
- Energy-efficiency investments

INTERESTED IN LEARNING ABOUT:

- Business models for energy-related projects
- Innovative Citizen Finance
- Revolving Funds
- Mobilising private investments
- Blended Finance

The Capacity Building Program will support the upskilling of public authorities and local communities across these key cross-cutting areas and the Key Target Sectors to enable successful PCED implementation and unlock the systemic transformation necessary to achieve climate neutrality.

If you want to know more:

Dresden Sustainable City of the future

Co-design of climate action plans

Dresden Citizen Participation Platform

neutralpath.eu/

2030
NEUTRALPATH

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